

CHALLENGE

- The wood board industry depends on the use of fossil-based binders that are mainly formaldehyde-based.
- Upcoming regulations foresee reduced formaldehyde emissions from furniture due to its effects on indoor air-quality.
- Alternative binders from renewable resources able to compete at industrial scale with incumbent chemicals do not exist yet.

Increasing global consumption and climate change call for innovative products that reduce greenhouse gas emissions and dependency on fossil resources.

SOLUTION

Develop and produce low VOC (volatile organic compound) emission bio-based binders for furniture mass production by:

- Substituting fossil-based chemicals with those from renewable resources.
- Using surplus feedstock sourced from European biorefineries.

Test and validate bio-based binders with leading wood board manufacturers for two product types:

- P2 particle board and
- medium density fibreboard

PARTNERS

Contacts:

Coordination & Communication:
Ana Babić, RTDS Group, susbind@rtds-group.com

Scientific Coordination:
Massimo Bregola, Cargill,
Massimo_bregola@cargill.com

@SUSBIND BBI

This project has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 792063.

Picture credits: © Cargill, Egger, RTDS Group, Shutterstock
Responsible for layout and content: RTDS Group

www.susbind.eu

www.susbind.eu

Sustainable bio-binders
for wood-based panels
from renewable resources

SUSBIND is a collaborative European research & innovation project addressing the need for more sustainable bio-based binders used for wood-based panel boards in the European furniture industry. The SUSBIND Consortium develops, produces and tests bio-based binders as an alternative to fossil-based binders currently used in furniture mass products.

OBJECTIVES

- Substitute fossil-based chemicals with those from renewable resources.
- Make use of surplus feedstock from European biorefineries including sugars and lipids.
- Reduce carbon footprint of furniture products to help mitigate climate change.
- Strengthen the European furniture industry through novel, cost-efficient eco-products.

SUSBIND in a nutshell

Start: 1st May 2018
 Duration: 4 years 4 months
 Budget: € 5.5 Million
 BBI-JU funding: € 4.1 Million
 Consortium: 11 partners

APPROACH

1 Selection of the sustainable starch-based and vegetable oil-based feedstock from bio-refineries.

2 Lab-scale studies on chemical and enzymatic synthesis of the most promising furfural and epoxy type binder components; Pilot assays for resin production.

3 Industrial testing of new bio-based wood board binders and subsequent products.

4 Economical & environmental sustainability

- Verify environmental and market regulatory requirements for the bio-based binder system.
- Ensure to produce a binder with a smaller carbon footprint and less human health impact.

OUTCOME

Novel bio-based binders from renewable resources for:

- P2 particle board
- medium density fibreboard